

COVID 19 and academia community cooperation: skills development fostering diversity, inclusion and equal opportunities

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Abstract

This paper intends to discuss the development of skills in higher education in the area of inclusion, equal opportunities and special educational needs associated with COVID 19. It is mainly a theoretical reflection with qualitative data that inform the review. The paper intends to present the state of legislative mandates in Portugal and the articulation with European recommendations and higher education regarding inclusion. It also focus on the understanding of the impact of COVID 19 in social organizations and how can higher education institutions help to develop skills in this reality, therefore increasing university-social organizations cooperation. Social organizations were interviewed through email and qualitative results are presented. In addition, international imperatives will be presented and their articulation with skills development in higher education in Portugal. Formal future implementation towards inclusion in Higher Education Institutions is key and 1) fostering skills, 2) adapting curricula, 3) training faculty members, 4) teaching and learning more problem solving in practice, more work-based learning, more service-learning and 5) deep cooperation with social organizations, are key factors towards fostering an implementation of inclusion in Higher Education Institutions. It is important to ensure that effective and urgent European solutions are found for responses to the pandemic in the area of adult education in inclusion, equal opportunities and educational needs in all areas but also towards development of policies of inclusion in higher education.

Keywords: Skills development; inclusion; equal opportunities; special educational needs; covid-19; university social organizations cooperation

1 Introduction

The COVID 19 pandemic has brought about considerable changes in our educational systems and major economic disruptions. The OECD Interim Economic Assessment (2020) emphasizes that coronavirus containment efforts have involved widespread quarantines and restrictions on mobility and work travel. The impacts of such restrictions are significant, including direct disruption to global supply chains, weaker final demand for imported goods and services, and the wider regional decline in international tourism and business travel. Therefore, the growth prospects are very uncertain and, currently, there are no precise assumptions for the future regarding the economy and employment. The relevance of this article has therefore been increased by the current global context. The paper intends to present the state of legislative mandates in Portugal and the articulation with European recommendations and higher education regarding inclusion. It also focus on the understanding of the impact of COVID 19 in social organizations and how can higher education institutions help to develop skills in this reality, therefore increasing university-social organizations cooperation.

2 Skills development in higher education in the area of inclusion, equal opportunities and special educational

Skills development in this area is even more crucial when economies face recession and the need for rapid adaptation, flexibility and problem solving - although skill development cannot be considered a panacea for such severe conditions, it can however, making a difference for the consortium by navigating these dire circumstances and trying to increase the chances of the consortium facing the pandemic with more capable responses such as the possibility of the project in question. According to data from the latest OECD report of OECD - Tackling Coronavirus COVID 19) | Contributing to a global effort: COVID-19: Protecting people and societies, the Coronavirus COVID-19 pandemic presents specific challenges for well-being people with disabilities, particularly in the dimensions of education, health and social life. The pandemic has introduced a very deep stress in the lives of people with disabilities, drastically altering their routines and significantly modifying the way they manage their daily lives. The United Nations in its latest report entitled "Pandemic COVID 19 and People with Disabilities" says that people with disabilities generally have more health care needs than others - both standard and disability-related needs - and therefore are more vulnerable to the impact of low quality or inaccessible services than other audiences. Although having a disability is unlikely to expose people to an increased risk of coronavirus, many people with disabilities have specific underlying conditions that make the disease more dangerous for them, including its social and individual development effects. In addition, the European Disability Forum in its open letter to the leaders of the European Union: Covid-19 - Inclusive Response to Disability, states that investment in the provision of services and support in this public is crucial and, consequently, maximum European solidarity is necessary to guarantee strengthening services. According to this letter, as is well known, health and social care systems are constantly underfunded across the EU. Investment in these services is essential and urgent to ensure that they can cope with the rising costs associated with the crisis. This contingency plan accelerated the transformation of the labor market and marked social support institutions as essential to the survival of a country in crisis. The interdependence of the population and these institutions makes the relevance of this investment in training, knowledge sharing and awareness raising within this theme evident. Mckinsey's latest April report entitled "Thinking about the next normal but making it work" demonstrates the need for organizations to find a balance between what they did before and what needs to happen in the new normal. The future is not what we thought it would be just a few months ago and according to the report it is important to assume that organizations should not assume that everything will be as it was before. It is crucial to find new ways to respond to the new problems that the pandemic poses. It is important to re - imagine the challenges that the future presents us. With the Coronavirus pandemic (COVID 19) collaboration, flexibility of solutions and inclusion need more than ever to be worked on and the financing of this project would make it possible to develop a very valid set of responses in the area of adult education that would allow to build responses to this pandemic more effectively. The Mckinsey report focuses on the need to deconstruct the usual traditional organizations and to design new non-traditional teams.

In 2017, the Portuguese State ended the lethargy regarding initiatives that focus on the inclusion of students with SEN in higher education. Order No. 10734/2017 creates the Working Group on Special Needs in Science, Technology and Higher Education (GT-NECTES, 2017), which makes a report with 67 recommendations. Of the indications made by the GT-NECTES, the highlight is the granting of a scholarship for people who prove they have 60% or more disability (Dec. Lei No. 8584/2017), which in the 2018/2019 academic year came to benefit around 400 students, and the Inclusion Desk creation project allocated. It is recommended to make essential information available in physical formats such as Braille, extended characters or simple language, as well as interpretation for Sign Language. Following Directive 2016/2102, it is a priority to make processes such as: registration, notifications and receipt of credentials, applications, interactive forms, as well as all types of information supporting the respective processes accessible - it is important to diagnose, carry out usability studies with users with some type of functional limitation and rectify the interactive interfaces and support information. It is also recommended that HEIs define welcoming practices, involving and valuing the student community / student associations in supporting students with special needs, either through peer group programs (mentored) or through volunteer programs. It is urgent to include in the HEIs a diagnosis of the study of measures for the implementation of specific teleworking or distance learning conditions for students or

workers with disabilities and accessibility of work materials and the electronic assessment system for workers with special educational needs. As mentioned by Claeys-Kulik, Jorgensen & Stober (2019) the lack of awareness between university and the community on issues of diversity and inclusion is an ongoing challenge, followed by a lack of funding and other resources, and the difficulty of identifying target groups.

The paper intends to present the state of legislative mandates in Portugal and the articulation with European recommendations and higher education regarding inclusion. It also focus on the understanding of the impact of COVID 19 in social organizations and how can higher education institutions help to develop skills in this reality, therefore increasing university-social organizations cooperation.

3 Method

3.1 Procedure and participants

This paper intends to present a research with three social organizational that work in inclusion, equal opportunities and special educational area. Qualitative data were collected in April 2020. The goal was to understand the impact of COVID 19 in their organizations and how could the higher education institutions help to develop skills in this reality. Social organizations were invited to participate in the research. The criterion used in these selection was the proximity with the university and involvement in previous common projects. The interviews focused on two key topics: current situation of social organization regarding their limitations on service and contributions of higher education institutions on competence development. Interviews were implemented through email. Qualitative results were analyzed using Bardin content analysis.

4 Results

Results from the social organization on neuromotor disability area informs that the time of confinement has, without a doubt, consequences for the physical and mental well-being of its users. More than 2 months without direct therapeutic intervention (with the maintenance of guidelines via telephone to the user or caregiver), will in the future be reflected in more motor setbacks and therefore more needs for support products or more complex adaptations. Professionals have demonstrated their ability to adapt, but face-to-face contact in the neuromotor area is essential. They are all anxious to return from the classroom activity. This being a new situation worldwide, there are practices in the field that have been shown to be more efficient in this situation. Therefore, relating to topic of contributions of higher education institutions on competence development this participant refers that universities can be very relevant in the exchange of experiences (benchlearning) and knowledge exchange, including with other countries in order to try to minimize the consequences for our users for so long without direct intervention. The faster they could articulate with other realities, the more quickly we will implement new strategies.

Results from the social organization on autism area reports that they have faced successive challenges in the context of this pandemic. Therefore, relating to the topic of contributions of higher education institutions on competence development this participant refers that universities would leverage innovation and institutional development and strengthen partnerships. The recipients of the organization's action are people with Autism Spectrum Disorder, clients that they describe as being the fringes of the most vulnerable population. Considering for instances the capacity and competences for the adoption of individual protection measures. Even this capacity to understand the need in these population are often compromised. In this sense, the access that this population has to the necessary care and support is small and compromises their current and future quality of life. The organization's technical team has been developing new intervention methodologies that, at the same time, guarantees public health, trying to minimize the required physical isolation, which implies changes in resources and conditions in the organization itself. All efforts will be made to maintain the inclusion and equal opportunities of people with Autism Spectrum Disorder. At this moment it is assumed by this organization that the role of higher education institutions on competence development is very relevant and crucial for the training of our professionals.

The social organization in the area of visual impairment was forced, in this context of prevention and containment of the pandemic, to suspend its in-person activity, which has had a significant impact on the daily

management of social response and on the relationship between employees, users, families and community partners. Visually impaired people have been particularly affected, seeing their dependence on others growing and exacerbating the fear associated with this threat to public health. Touch is essential in the relationship that these people establish with the world around them, making compliance with the rules for preventing coronavirus infection very difficult. Social isolation also tends to be experienced more intensely, especially in the case of users who do not master the new information and communication technologies. The public's already usual vulnerability is, of course, exacerbated. The technical team has developed its activity based on remote communication with users, which constrains the support provided and the quality of the relationship established. Interlocution with other professionals and services has been extremely important, helping to solve the problems that, at each moment, users are confronted. The resumption of face-to-face activity is already being prepared, but they anticipate great difficulties in view of the type of work developed and the characteristics of the response, developed in the natural contexts of people's lives and with a strong involvement of families and other community resources. Compliance with social detachment proves to be especially challenging and the role of universities could be the new practices to be developed and are yet to be developed and implemented. University-social cooperation is crucial for learning and developing towards more effective European responses.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

Claeys-Kulik, Jorgensen & Stober (2019) stated that the lack of awareness between university and the community on issues of diversity and inclusion is an ongoing challenge, followed by a lack of funding and other resources, and the difficulty of identifying target groups. This report, which considers the education of professionals necessary, the training of administrative teams and teams of teachers and researchers, with a view to raising the level of awareness and providing tools and concrete approaches to deal with diversity. Ultimately, this will promote inclusiveness in the learning, teaching and research environments. Part of this relevance would be to continue moving the discourse on diversity from a challenge to be solved under previous conditions of quality and excellence. Several leading European universities have already explicitly assumed this position, as they realize that, by ensuring equitable treatment, they immediately improve their learning environment and their research. Universities should intend to take this step and continue to improve its learning and research environment and in its exploration and dissemination plan, to argue precisely the significant improvement of its teaching and learning processes. Universities should develop alternative curricula fully integrated with the special needs of the social organizations. This particular result, which according to our knowledge to date, is scarce in the context of higher education in Portugal, would allow Universities to advance in terms of training and promoting equal opportunities. IPVC, for instances, intends to increase the active cooperation projects between with social organizations allowing for greater synergistic exchanges between mutual needs, achieving more beneficial joint solutions for the area of disability, increasing the likelihood of transferring the positive results towards skills development and the efficiency of the learning outcomes. When designing these alternative curricula, universities should take into account the technical infrastructure of the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), which should guarantee the accessibility of learning materials and the electronic assessment system for students with special educational needs. Universities should have the responsibility to provide students with adequate library resources (ie an electronic library service) and any necessary training as an institutional responsibility. Study programs should include virtual laboratories designed to ensure the acquisition of specific learning outcomes. According to Heiman and Preceel (2003) practice in teaching and developing skills in disabled learners is very relevant. Regarding academic strategies students with learning disabilities they preferred additional oral explanations or visual explanations, whereas nondisabled students preferred more written examples. Additional effort should be made by universities to tackle these demanding's regarding inclusion of students with special needs in higher education. Skills development appears to be more relevant and during examinations, the students with special needs had difficulty concentrating and were concerned about lack of time. Wray and Houghton (2019) showed that government policy (in UK) hadn't such a relevant effect on HEIS practice, however the study made clear the efforts made by faculty members to support disabled students. These efforts were based on values associated with providing an equitable experience for all students. Faculty members were able to exercise discretion

responding to disabled students without significant influence from institutional managers, national legislation or broader policy discourse. Therefore, there is a long journey to overcome regarding policies and afterwards implementation on higher education institutions. Wray and Houghton (2019) show that faculty members are tackling with success and human values disabilities in higher education, however more is needed.

Formal future implementation towards inclusion in Higher Education Institutions is key and 1) fostering skills, 2) adapting curricula, 3) training faculty members, 4) teaching and learning more problem solving in practice, more work-based learning, more service-learning and 5) deep cooperation with social organizations, are key factors towards fostering an implementation of inclusion in Higher Education Institutions.

6 Conclusion

It is relevant that higher education projects involve different stakeholders with different and relevant roles in the area of inclusion, equal opportunities and special educational needs. This will allow to create a direct impact on regional political measures, assuring also the participation of the main regional decision-makers. It is important to ensure that effective and urgent European solutions are found for responses to the pandemic in the area of adult education in inclusion, equal opportunities and educational needs in all areas but also towards development of policies in higher education. Also, Higher Education Institutions that work thoroughly these issues should develop formal future implementation towards inclusion fostering skills, adapting curricula, training faculty members, teaching and learning more problem solving in practice, more work-based learning, more service-learning and increase cooperation with social organizations, key factors towards fostering an implementation of diversity in Higher Education.

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